
MRI ACUTE/SUB-ACUTE ISCHEMIC STROKE SEGMENTATION WITH DEEP LEARNING: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

The segmentation of ischemic stroke lesions from Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) images using deep learning (DL) techniques has emerged as a critical area of research in medical imaging. This article provides a comprehensive review of the current state-of-the-art methodologies in this domain, focusing on the advancements and challenges inherent in this field. Our review focuses on studies that utilize DL models for segmenting acute and sub-acute ischemic stroke lesions using MRI modalities. By systematically analyzing research from 2020 to August 2024, we aim to clarify the advancements in the published models' effectiveness and provide a performance benchmark. This review stands out by comprehensively analyzing all the studies in this field, beyond the scope of prior reviews focused only on key publications. Additionally, this work serves as a comprehensive reference for researchers by compiling all relevant datasets, MRI modalities, evaluation metrics, loss functions, input data dimensionality, preprocessing, and augmentation techniques employed for this task. Additionally, we identify the challenges in this field and highlight the existing research gaps, in addition to proposing some directions for future work to enhance the effectiveness and accuracy of DL models in stroke lesion segmentation.

Keywords Acute/Sub-Acute Ischemic Stroke · Medical Image Segmentation · Deep Learning · Systematic Review · ISLES · MRI · Diffusion Weighted Images

1 Introduction

Brain stroke is a sudden interruption of blood flow in the brain, leading to a lack of oxygen and nutrients to brain tissue. This can be caused by a blockage, which then is called ischemic stroke, or bleeding, which on the other hand is called hemorrhagic stroke [1]. Ischemic strokes are the most common type, accounting for approximately 88% of all stroke cases, and they are the most known life-threatening neurological condition [2, 3]. Stroke typically evolves along multiple stages. The acute stage refers to effects occurring typically a few hours/days after stroke onset, while the

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sub-acute stage encompasses the period of two weeks to three months following stroke onset. In contrast, the chronic stage is characterized by long-term effects occurring months or years after the initial insult [4]. Other classification schemes use a much refined five-stage classification, including hyperacute (within 24 hours after stroke onset), acute (within two weeks), early subacute (from two weeks to three months), late subacute (from three months to six months), and chronic stage (after six months). Figure 1 presents a widely used classification of stroke types, also adopted here, with the categories highlighted in blue indicating the specific stroke types and stages that are the focus of this review.

Figure 1: Taxonomy of stroke types.

Stroke patients typically undergo neuroimaging techniques to differentiate between ischemic and hemorrhagic strokes in addition to identifying the location and the size of the stroke, as accurate diagnosis is critical for determining the appropriate treatment. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and computed tomography (CT) are commonly used for this purpose, each providing unique insights into brain health. MRI, known for its superior soft tissue contrast, is particularly useful when the diagnosis is uncertain or when more detailed imaging is required. It can offer more comprehensive information than CT, particularly regarding the location, timing, and underlying mechanisms of the stroke [5].

An MRI sequence, or MRI modality, refers to a specific configuration of pulse sequences and pulsed field gradients, leading to a distinct appearance in the generated image. Within MRI modalities, diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI) is especially valuable, because it can detect early changes in brain tissue caused by ischemia with a high contrast, helping to assess the full extent of the stroke’s impact [6].

Brain stroke segmentation is the process of precisely identifying and segmenting the stroke-affected regions, called lesions, in neuroimaging data. Accurate stroke segmentation is crucial because timely and precise identification of stroke lesions directly impacts diagnosis, treatment planning, and patient outcomes. Early and accurate detection of stroke-affected areas allows clinicians to determine the type, severity, and location of the stroke, which is essential for deciding appropriate interventions such as thrombolysis or thrombectomy. Misidentification or delay in segmentation can lead to ineffective treatment, potentially resulting in severe neurological damage, disability, or even death. Thus, reliable stroke segmentation is critical in improving survival rates and reducing long-term complications [7].

To detect and segment diffusion abnormalities in ischemic acute strokes, historically, various traditional machine learning algorithms have been used, such as support vector machine and random forest [8]. Recently, remarkable progress in deep learning (DL) for brain lesion segmentation has been made, outperforming traditional methods. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have played a pivotal role in this advancement by efficiently learning spatial hierarchies of features from imaging data, which is crucial for accurate segmentation [9]. U-Net, a notable DL model, has made a significant improvement in the area of segmentation by incorporating coarse features through skip connections [10]. Further U-Net variants were adopted later to enhance feature utilization and focus more on local features [8].

Recently, there has been a surge of interest in introducing transformers to vision tasks, following the great success of transformers in natural language processing (NLP). Vision transformers (ViT) were proposed by Dosovitskiy et al. [11] for image classification, splitting an image into multiple linearly embedded patches and feeding them into a standard transformer with positional embeddings, leading to an impressive performance on ImageNet [12]. In semantic segmentation, Zheng et al. [13] proposed SETR to demonstrate the feasibility of using transformers in this task, adopting ViT as a backbone and incorporating several CNN decoders to enlarge feature resolution.

Between 2020 and 2024, 10 reviews have been identified in this field [2, 4, 5, 6, 8, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18], addressing various aspects of acute-subacute ischemic stroke segmentation. Most of these reviews primarily focus on listing the key papers published in this area. In contrast, this review distinguishes itself by providing a comprehensive examination of all studies in the field of acute-subacute ischemic MRI segmentation, regardless of their publication venue impact. It also offers an extensive benchmarking of model performance and an in-depth analysis of factors influencing performance,

including input data dimensionality, loss functions, preprocessing methods, and augmentation techniques across the reviewed studies.

In this article, we discuss MRI acute/sub-acute ischemic stroke segmentation by systematically reviewing the literature from 2020 onward, aiming to:

- Provide a summary of all the methods published in the field, and provide a benchmark for their performance and effectiveness.
- Propose a comprehensive taxonomy that classifies the reviewed models based on their method and category.
- Serve as a comprehensive reference for researchers by compiling all available datasets, MRI modalities, evaluation metrics, loss functions, preprocessing, and augmentation techniques used by the published articles.
- Identify ongoing challenges in the field and highlight critical research gaps, and offer future directions to improve the effectiveness and accuracy of the deep learning models in this field.

2 METHODS AND MATERIALS

This systematic review adopts the methodology outlined by Tranfield et al. [19], encompassing five key stages, and adheres to the guidelines of the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) checklist and flow chart [20].

2.1 Data Sources and Search Strategy

We performed a comprehensive search for published papers from Jan/2020 to Sep/2024 across eight academic databases. The keywords were applied to both titles and abstracts, with the full text not being reviewed at this stage. Detailed information about the databases, keywords, and number of records retrieved per database is provided in Table 1.

Table 1: Databases searched, keywords used, and number of records retrieved per database (Jan 2020 – Sep 2024).

Databases (# of Records)	Keywords
Google Scholar (412)	[("Stroke" OR "Lesion" OR "Acute Ischemic" OR "sub-Acute Ischemic") AND ("Segmentation" OR "Feature Extraction") AND ("MRI" OR "Magnetic Resonance Imaging")]
PubMed/Medline (183)	
IEEE Xplore (93)	
ACM Digital Library (44)	
ScienceDirect (56)	
Web of Science (67)	
arXIV (52)	
Embase (71)	

2.2 Study Selection

We established our inclusion and exclusion criteria for this survey, requiring all selected studies to meet the inclusion criteria and excluding any study that meets any exclusion criteria. Table 2 outlines these inclusion/exclusion criteria.

The initial search across all the aforementioned databases yielded 978 articles. After reviewing the titles and removing duplicates, this number was reduced to 255 articles. We then applied the inclusion and exclusion criteria to the abstracts, narrowing the selection to 85 articles for further evaluation. In the final stage, we retrieved and thoroughly reviewed the full-text versions of these studies. After careful assessment, 60 articles met all the criteria and were included in the final analysis. Additionally, we reviewed the references in the included studies to find any relevant papers that might have been missed during the initial search. This process is illustrated in the PRISMA flowchart shown in Figure 2.

Moreover, from 2015 to Sep/2024, 31 private datasets were identified but they were excluded from further analysis and benchmarking. Additionally, we identified 10 prior reviews in this area.

2.3 Data Extraction and Analysis

The process of extracting the information was done manually, and the data was managed and analyzed using MS Excel spreadsheets. Any unclear or insufficiently explained details were left blank. After careful examination and analysis of the included studies, we extracted: the dataset(s) used, the MRI modality(s) utilized, the format of the input data (2D

Table 2: Inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Studies involving human subject cases.	Studies involving animal data.
Studies published in English between 2020 and 2024.	Studies published in languages other than English or published before 2020.
Studies involving acute and/or subacute ischemic strokes.	Studies involving chronic ischemic, hemorrhagic, or any other kind of strokes or brain lesions.
Studies utilizing MRI data.	Studies that did not utilize MRI data.
Studies proposing DL-based segmentation models.	Studies proposing non-DL-based segmentation models or other statistical methods.
Studies discussing stroke segmentation, whether for training or testing the model.	Studies focused solely on stroke classification or detection, without addressing segmentation.
Studies utilizing both novel and publicly available models.	Studies focused exclusively on stroke treatment or biochemistry.

slices or 3D scans), the loss function(s) used, the overall model’s architecture, a summary of the model’s methodology, the preprocessing techniques applied, the data augmentation strategies implemented, and the evaluation metrics utilized.

3 FINDINGS

In this section, we will discuss the challenges surrounding this field, in addition to summarizing our findings in terms of the datasets, MRI modalities, input data formats, evaluation metrics, loss functions, preprocessing techniques, and data augmentation strategies. It is important to note that this summary includes only the elements that were actually utilized in the reviewed studies.

3.1 Challenges of Stroke Segmentation

Accurate segmentation of stroke lesions presents several challenges, many of which stem from the inherent complexity of the task and the limitations of available data. The challenges can be summarized as follows:

Scarcity of Labeled Datasets: Annotating medical images is a labor-intensive process that requires expert knowledge. This scarcity of labeled data presents a significant challenge, as supervised learning models rely heavily on accurately labeled datasets to achieve optimal performance. The lack of large labeled publicly available datasets for acute stroke cases further complicates the problem, making it difficult to train robust models that can be generalized across patient populations [4].

Data Imbalance: In stroke imaging, the size of healthy tissue often vastly outweighs the size of lesions (i.e. number of abnormal voxels), leading to imbalanced datasets. This imbalance skews the learning process of deep learning models, resulting in a bias towards healthy tissue and potentially overlooking or misidentifying smaller stroke lesions.

Lesions Variability: Acute and sub-acute ischemic stroke lesions vary greatly in size, shape, intensity, texture, and location, making their segmentation particularly challenging. These variations require models to adapt to a broad range of lesion characteristics, further complicating the development of a one-size-fits-all solution.

Small Lesion Segmentation: Acute and sub-acute stroke lesions are sometimes small and numerous. As the depth of neural networks increases, they tend to obtain deeper abstract information but at the cost of lower feature resolution, which can cause small lesions to vanish in the down-sampling steps. Selecting an appropriate network depth, input image size, and kernel configuration is crucial to strike a balance between capturing relevant features and maintaining resolution [4]. On the contrary, using small input patches might fail to capture contextual information from larger lesions, especially near the boundaries [5].

Heterogeneity and Comparative Analysis: Many studies use private or public datasets with different data quality, making cross-study comparisons challenging [8]. This variability in data quality is more pronounced in multi-site studies, where differences in imaging protocols and equipment can introduce inconsistencies [4]. Moreover, the Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) tends to positively correlate with lesion size, meaning that as the lesion size decreases, the DSC decreases as well. In some cases, even a small DSC value may be considered a good result, particularly for very small lesions [21].

Figure 2: PRISMA flowchart.

Transfer Learning and Fine-Tuning: Transfer learning has been widely used in image-based tasks to leverage pre-trained models. However, a critical question arises in stroke lesion segmentation: Is it appropriate to fine-tune a model trained on natural images, rather than medical images? While transfer learning can accelerate the training process and reduce the need for large medical datasets, fine-tuning a model designed for a different domain might result in suboptimal performance when applied to medical images due to the differences in the learned features.

MRI modalities provide a range of contrasts and functional information, each useful for different aspects of brain imaging, particularly in the context of stroke diagnosis and segmentation. Figure 3 shows some examples of the most used MRI modalities. Diffusion-Weighted Imaging (DWI) is commonly used as a standard in stroke segmentation due to its sensitivity to restricted water diffusion, which makes it effective in detecting ischemic changes in the brain. DWI is often complemented by Apparent Diffusion Coefficient (ADC) maps, derived from DWI images, and Attenuated Inversion Recovery (FLAIR) images. ADC helps to refine the identification of true diffusion restriction by quantifying this diffusion, making it particularly useful for emphasizing tissues with higher diffusion [22]. FLAIR suppresses the cerebrospinal fluid signal, which helps to provide clearer images of the brain structures and other abnormalities [23]. Together, these three modalities—DWI, ADC, and FLAIR—are sometimes used as three-channel input data [22]. These modalities provide a detailed and comprehensive view of brain structure and function.

Figure 3: Some examples of the MRI modalities.

Furthermore, T1-weighted (T1) images offer detailed anatomical views, highlighting fat and white matter, while T1 contrast-enhanced (T1c) images are used to visualize blood-brain barrier disruptions by enhancing areas with gadolinium contrast [24]. Magnetization-Prepared Rapid Gradient-Echo (T1-MPRAGE) is often employed for high-resolution anatomical imaging [25, 26]. T2-weighted (T2) images, in contrast, are sensitive to water content, making them valuable for detecting edema and fluid distribution in the brain [24, 25]. Also, zero b-value-weighted (b0) imaging is part of DWI, serving as a baseline (b-value of 0) for comparison with diffusion-weighted images [25]. Low b-value-weighted imaging (LOWB) enhances perfusion effects and tissue contrast [27], while high b-value (b1000) imaging detects diffusion restrictions, crucial for identifying ischemic lesions [28]. Furthermore, Perfusion-Weighted Imaging (PWI) with its derived maps such as Cerebral Blood Flow (CBF), Cerebral Blood Volume (CBV), Mean Transit Time (MTT), Time to Peak (TTP), and Tmax are used to assess blood flow dynamics within the brain, which are critical for identifying regions at risk of infarction [26]. In addition, Susceptibility-Weighted Imaging (SWI) offers high sensitivity to blood products and venous structures [25]. Finally, another variety of ADC called exponential ADC (eADC), which simply equals $100 \times e^{-ADC}$, suppresses signals from low ADC regions [29].

In Figure 4, we propose a categorization for the various imaging modalities commonly used in stroke segmentation, specifically within MRI, detailing their relationships and subtypes. The highlighted blocks in blue indicate the most used MRI modalities. In both public and private datasets, DWI is the most commonly used MRI modality for acute stroke segmentation, followed by ADC as the second most utilized, and FLAIR ranks third in the frequency of use.

Figure 4: Categorization of MRI imaging modalities.

3.2 Publicly Available Datasets

This section provides an overview of available MRI datasets used for stroke lesion segmentation in acute/sub-acute ischemic stroke patients. Each dataset includes various imaging modalities and differs in the number of cases it contains. A summary of key details for these datasets is presented in Table 3, along with the number of studies that have utilized them. In addition, we visualize the key MRI modalities, that are often used by researchers of each dataset in Figure 5.

The datasets that discuss CT-based data, such as ISLES 2018 [30], ISLES 2024 [31], APIS [32], and AISD [33] were excluded from this review. Also, chronic ischemic stroke datasets like ATLAS v2.0 [34], and unannotated MRI datasets like the one provided by APIS [32], were also excluded from this review.

The Ischemic Stroke Lesion Segmentation (ISLES) challenge, part of the MICCAI conference, has released several publicly available datasets over the years, specifically in 2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2022, and 2024 [22, 24, 26, 31]. The main goal of these challenges is to evaluate the performance of automated methods in accurately generating lesion segmentation masks from different imaging modalities. Each iteration of the challenge emphasizes different objectives

Figure 5: Examples of the datasets' images and their lesion masks.

Table 3: Summary of the included datasets.

Dataset	Stroke Type	Train Cases	Test Cases*	MRI Modalities
SISS	Sub-acute	28	36	T1, T2, FLAIR, DWI.
SPES	Acute	30	20	T1c, T2, DWI, CBF, CBV, Tmax, TTP.
ISLES17	Acute	43	32	ADC, rBF, rBV, MTT, Tmax, TTP, Raw PWI.
ISLES22	Acute/sub-acute	250	150	DWI, ADC, FLAIR.
JHUS	Acute/sub-acute	1849	–	DWI, B0, ADC, T1, T1-MPRAGE, T2, FLAIR, SWI, PWI.

*The testing cases ground-truths are hidden from the public.

and offers distinct image modalities. In this study, we focus on the MRI-based ISLES datasets, particularly ISLES 2015 (both SISS and SPES) [24], ISLES 2017 [26], and ISLES 2022 [22].

The Anatomical Tracings of Lesions After Stroke (ATLAS) v2.0 [34] dataset includes 655 T1 MRI ischemic stroke cases with corresponding annotated masks, featuring 57 acute and sub-acute cases, with the remaining 582 cases being chronic strokes. For a study using the ATLAS dataset to be considered here, it must report evaluation metrics for acute/sub-acute cases separately from the chronic cases. While this dataset initially appeared promising for inclusion in this review, it was ultimately excluded because none of the studies utilizing ATLAS v2.0 distinguished these 57 acute/sub-acute cases from the remaining 582 chronic stroke cases or used them for cross-validation against the ISLES datasets.

3.2.1 ISLES 2015-SISS

The ISLES 2015 dataset, as described by Maier et al. [24], consists of two sub-challenges presented at MICCAI 2015: Sub-Acute Ischemic Stroke Lesion Segmentation (SISS) and Acute Stroke Perfusion Estimation (SPES). The SISS [24] dataset comprises 64 cases of sub-acute ischemic stroke. These cases were gathered from two separate medical centers,

resulting in variations in image resolution. Each case includes four MRI modalities: T1, T2, DWI, and FLAIR. The images have a voxel size of 1 mm³, with resolutions of 230×230×(153 or 154) voxels. Preprocessing steps, such as skull-stripping and resampling to an isotropic space, were applied, with all modalities registered to the FLAIR modality.

3.2.2 ISLES 2015-SPES

The SPES [24] dataset contains 50 cases of acute ischemic stroke. The MRI scans have a voxel size of 2x2x2 mm³, with resolutions of 96×110×(71,72, or 78). Each case includes seven different imaging modalities: T1c, T2, DWI, CBF, CBV, TTP, and Tmax. For each patient, two distinct masks are provided: one delineating the penumbra, and the other identifying the ischemic core. Preprocessing steps such as skull-stripping and resampling to an isotropic space, were applied, with all modalities registered to the T1c modality.

3.2.3 ISLES 2017

The ISLES 2017 dataset [26], an extension of the ISLES 2016 dataset, includes 75 acute ischemic stroke cases. Each case contains a raw 4D PWI, five 3D MRI perfusion maps (rCBF, rCBV, MTT, TTP, Tmax), and one 3D MRI diffusion map (ADC). Preprocessing steps such as including skull-stripping and image registration. The MRI scans have varying sizes, including (128, 192, or 256)×(128, 192, or 256)×(19, 24, 25, or 30).

3.2.4 ISLES 2022

The ISLES 2022 dataset, published by Hernandez Petzsche et al. [22], consists of data from 400 cases of acute and sub-acute ischemic strokes sourced from three different medical centers. The dataset was acquired from three medical centers and includes three MRI modalities: DWI, ADC, and FLAIR. All MRI data were skull-stripped, de-identified, and standardized in MNI space. The resolution of the cases varies significantly, with heights and widths ranging between 112 and 256 pixels, and depths ranging between 25 and 76 pixels. TABLE 4 provides further details on the MRI resolutions in this dataset, listing the frequencies of each resolution from most to least common. Height and width are the first and second dimensions, respectively, where depth is the third dimension.

Table 4: ISLES 2022 MRI cases resolutions.

	Height and Width	Depth
Resolution	112, 128, 192, 115, 256, 130, 170, 122	73, 72, 25, 30, 75, 65, 28, 74, 33, 70, 76, 27, 63
Frequencies	188, 31, 23, 3, 2, 1, 1, 1	95, 94, 27, 24, 2, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1

3.2.5 JHUS

Johns Hopkins University’s (JHUS) [25] dataset includes 2880 MRI cases, covering hemorrhagic, ischemic acute, and early subacute strokes with expert manual lesion segmentations. Collected over a decade using 11 different MRI scanners, the dataset features 1849 MRIs depicting acute/early-sub-acute ischemic strokes with visible lesions and 540 hemorrhagic stroke cases. For each patient, DWI, b0, and ADC images were provided, with most of patients also having additional MRI modalities. Nearly half of the patients received intravenous thrombolysis (IVtPA) before the MRI scan. The DWI images were registered to MNI space, underwent skull-stripping, and were resampled to a voxel size of 1 mm³, with all the cases standardized to a size of 181×219×181.

3.3 Private Datasets

Furthermore, 31 additional studies [27, 28, 29, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47, 48, 49, 50, 51, 52, 53, 54, 55, 56, 57, 58, 59, 60, 61, 62] focused on MRI acute/sub-acute ischemic stroke lesion segmentation using private datasets. The sample sizes of these MRI private datasets ranged between 18 and 6937 patients. These datasets have fewer MRI modalities (1–4), with the DWI modality being the most utilized one, compared to the public datasets (3–9). The architectures of these studies were excluded from the analysis, and they were mostly variants of U-Net. Only seven studies [28, 29, 35, 44, 58, 59, 60] validated their results using the public datasets, and thus, were included in the analysis. Table 5 presents an overview of these private datasets, organized by the year of publication over the last decade, and includes the number of patient cases and the corresponding MRI modalities employed.

Table 5: Overview of the private datasets.

Article	Year	Cases	MRI Modalities
[37]	2015	37	DWI, FLAIR, T1
[36]	2016	18	FLAIR, T1, T2, T1c
[38]	2018	142	DWI
[39]	2017	741	DWI, ADC
[40]	2018	242	DWI, ADC
[41]	2018	192	DWI
[42]	2018	108	DWI, ADC
[27]	2019	267	DWI, ADC, LOWB
[43]	2019	429	DWI, ADC
[44]	2020	29	DWI, T2
[45]	2020	192	DWI
[46]	2020	192	DWI, ADC
[47]	2020	355	DWI, FLAIR
[48]	2020	257	DWI
[49]	2020	28	DWI, FLAIR, T1, T1c
[63]	2021	280	DWI, ADC, b0
[50]	2021	582	DWI, ADC
[51]	2021	6937	DWI, ADC
[52]	2022	34	-
[53]	2022	875	DWI, eADC
[54]	2022	216	DWI, T1
[29]	2023	930	DWI, eADC
[55], [56]	2023	99	DWI, eADC
[57]	2023	455	DWI, ADC
[58]	2023	-	-
[59]	2023	86	-
[60]	2023	44	DWI, FLAIR
[28]	2023	120	DWI, b0, b1000, T2
[61]	2023	316	DWI, ADC
[62]	2024	218	DWI
[35]	2024	70	DWI

MRI scans are inherently 3-dimensional (3D) but can be divided into 2-dimensional (2D) slices in different orientations, such as axial, coronal, or sagittal views, where axial slices are usually used. Segmentation models can utilize either 2D or 3D input data, depending on their design. It is crucial to evaluate segmentation performance using 3D images. For models that output 2D slices, these slices must be stacked to create a 3D volume for accurate comparison with the ground truth. Otherwise, evaluation metrics like the DSC can be skewed, producing overly high or low values. For instance, slices without any lesions may yield a DSC of 1 or 0, leading to inaccurate performance assessment. The choice between 2D and 3D data depends on the study’s objectives, available resources, and the complexity of the lesions being segmented. For researchers prioritizing computational efficiency or working with smaller datasets, 2D data may be the better option. However, when the aim is to achieve maximum accuracy in capturing volumetric stroke lesions, 3D data is often preferred, despite the increased computational demands. Table 6 outlines the advantages and limitations of both data types.

3.3.1 2D Slices

Processing 2D data requires less memory and computational resources, making model training faster and more accessible for researchers with limited hardware. Additionally, the reduced complexity of 2D models leads to fewer trainable parameters, which often results in quicker convergence and reliable performance without the need for large datasets [64]. The use of 2D slices also allows for straightforward data augmentation techniques, such as rotations, flips, and translations. Furthermore, using 2D slices provides more data, which is beneficial when working with smaller datasets. However, because stroke lesions can span across multiple slices, relying solely on 2D data may result in a loss of

Table 6: Categories of segmented pixels compared with ground truth pixels.

	2D images	3D images
Advantages	Better computational efficiency. Simplified model architectures. Easier data augmentation. Significantly more data. Shorter training time.	Preservation of spatial context.
Limitations	Loss of spatial context.	Increased computational demands. Longer training time.

critical spatial information, potentially reducing the model’s accuracy in capturing the full extent and shape of lesions, particularly for larger or irregularly shaped strokes [5], [64].

3.3.2 3D Volumes

Using 3D data preserves the spatial relationships between slices, which is essential for accurately segmenting complex and diffuse lesions that extend across multiple slices, leading to more precise segmentation. However, 3D data is significantly more computationally demanding, requiring substantial memory and processing power, which can be a huge limitation [14]. Additionally, the increased number of parameters in 3D models results in longer training times and a higher risk of overfitting, particularly when the dataset is small or lacks diversity.

3.4 Preprocessing Techniques

Preprocessing is a crucial step in medical image segmentation, ensuring that input data is standardized and optimized for model performance. In this section, we present a comprehensive overview of all the identified 17 preprocessing techniques employed in the reviewed studies, each contributing to enhancing image quality, reducing noise, and facilitating accurate feature extraction to improve segmentation. Additionally, Figure 6 shows some preprocessing techniques, demonstrating how they transform the original image to enhance its quality and suitability for analysis.

The preprocessing techniques can be grouped into several categories, the first is the spatial operations category, which includes processes like cropping, resampling, resizing, reorientation, and intensity registration. Image Cropping involves trimming the image to focus on the region of interest, typically removing background areas and keeping the brain area. Resampling to Uniform Voxel Size (RSM) adjusts voxel dimensions to a standard size, to 1x1x1mm for reviewed studies, to ensure uniformity across different scans and enable more effective model training. Image Resizing, or rescaling, adjusts the dimensions of an image by changing the number of pixels or voxels, typically to fit a specific resolution or input size required by the model, without altering the spatial resolution of the image. Image Reorientation re-aligns the images to a standard orientation, ensuring consistent spatial alignment across different datasets, which facilitates more accurate comparison and analysis. Image Registration aligns images from different time points or modalities to a common coordinate space. Registration or spatial normalization to MNI (Montreal Neurological Institute) [65] template is the most famous one, facilitating comparisons and analysis across different studies by using a common anatomical reference.

Figure 6: Image preprocessing examples.

The second category focuses on adjusting image intensity, such as normalization and correction. Intensity Normalization, or Normalization (Norm) for short, adjusts the intensity values across scans to a common range, ensuring that variations in scanner settings or patient characteristics do not interfere with the segmentation process. There are four common normalizations, which are Non-zero Mask Normalization, Z-score Normalization, Gaussian Normalization, and Min-Max Normalization. Intensity clipping (Clip) ensures that the data reflects meaningful physiological information by

restricting values within biologically meaningful ranges. For instance, Tmax values are clipped to [0, 20 seconds], and ADC values to $[0, 2600] \times 10^{-6} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$ [66, 67]. Bias Field Correction (BFC) corrects intensity non-uniformities in MRI images caused by scanner inhomogeneities, ensuring that the segmentation model can accurately differentiate between tissue types without being misled by imaging artifacts.

The third category targets noise and artifact reduction to enhance image quality, which includes noise reduction, Gaussian smoothing, and outlier removal. Noise Reduction (NR) removes or reduces image noise, improving the clarity of the scan and making it easier for the model to focus on relevant features. Gaussian Smoothing (GS) applies a Gaussian filter to reduce noise. Outlier Removal (OR) filters out extreme intensity values that may distort the segmentation process, ensuring that the model only focuses on relevant and accurate data.

The fourth category involves brain region extraction and feature extraction, such as skull stripping, patch extraction, and gradient entropy strategy. Skull Stripping (SS) involves removing the skull and other non-brain tissues from the MRI images to isolate the brain region. Patch Extraction (PE) involves dividing the images into smaller, manageable patches, allowing the model to focus on localized regions of interest. Gradient Entropy Strategy (GH) [68] patch extraction by utilizing entropy-based methods to prioritize patches with higher information content, is particularly helpful in identifying small or subtle stroke lesions.

Finally, the fifth category centers around histogram-based adjustments, emphasizing intensity distribution and contrast enhancement. Histogram Thresholding (HisT) [69] segments images by identifying intensity thresholds, separating foreground elements (lesions) from the background based on intensity distributions. Histogram-based Clustering (HisC) [70] clusters voxel intensities based on their histogram distribution, allowing the model to segment regions with similar intensity values, which can be useful for identifying lesion boundaries in noisy images. Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) [71] enhances the contrast of the MRI image by adjusting the histogram of intensity values, particularly useful in highlighting lesion regions that may have low contrast in the original scan.

3.5 Augmentation Strategies

To improve model robustness, enhance generalization, and increase data diversity with greater variations, augmentation techniques are often applied. In this subsection, we identified 13 augmentation techniques used in the reviewed studies. These techniques can be categorized into several categories based on their characteristics and objectives. Each category plays a specific role in transforming the data to help the model learn more effectively from limited or imbalanced data. Furthermore, Figure 7 showcases some augmentation techniques, illustrating how they modify the original image to enhance data diversity and robustness.

Figure 7: Image augmentation examples.

The first category is the geometric transformations, which focus on altering the spatial arrangement or structure of the image, such as image rotation, flipping, zooming, cropping, shifting, and shearing. Image Rotation involves rotating the image by specified degrees (e.g., 30° , 90° , 180° , or 270°), allowing the model to learn from different orientations of the data. Image Flipping, or image mirroring, including Horizontal Flipping (HF) and Vertical Flipping (VF), introduces variations in image orientation to make the model more robust to different spatial arrangements of lesions. Image Zooming, and sometimes referred to as image Scaling, changes the size of the object by zooming in or out, which helps the model learn to detect the object regardless of its size. Random Cropping (RC), where cropping randomly selects subregions of the image to help the model focus on different parts of the scan. Image Shifting moves the entire image by a specified number of pixels or a fraction of its dimensions, which ensures that the location of objects within the image doesn't affect performance. Image Shearing shifts one part of the image relative to another, creating a slanted

view, which introduces non-linear transformations that improve the model’s ability to recognize lesions under various distortions. Ashtari et al. [72] combined multiple geometric transformations and made them to be applied randomly in a method called Random Affine Transformations (RAT). Gómez et al. [73] employed random grid and optical distortions, where grid distortion involves non-linear warping through grid point shifts, and optical distortion mimics lens or scanning artifacts, modifying image geometry.

The second category focuses on simulating anatomical variations, like elastic deformation and image smoothing. Elastic Deformation (ED) stretches or distorts images in a non-rigid way, simulating anatomical variability and enhancing the model’s ability to generalize across different patient anatomies [74]. Image Smoothing reduces noise and small image artifacts, allowing the model to focus on the essential structural features.

The third category focuses on handling noise and imperfections in images, such as Gaussian blur and noise. Gaussian Blur (GB) smooths the image by reducing detail, while Gaussian Noise (GN) adds random noise to the image. These techniques help the model become more resilient to image noise and imperfections in real-world data [72, 74].

The last category involves adjustments in intensity and contrast, like brightness and contrast adjustments, and gamma transform. Brightness Adjustment (BA) and Contrast Adjustment (CA) involve altering the brightness and contrast of the image, allowing the model to train on data that simulates different scanner settings, enhancing its robustness to intensity variations [74]. Gamma Transform (GT), or gamma correction, adjusts the gamma value of the image, controlling the brightness levels to enhance feature visibility, especially in images with low contrast between lesions and surrounding tissue [74].

3.6 Quantitative Evaluation Metrics

Quantitative evaluation of segmentation models is essential for understanding how accurately a model categorizes pixels or voxels into either of the two classes: Lesion or No-Lesion. This evaluation is particularly crucial in the medical field, where precise segmentation can significantly impact diagnosis and treatment planning. In this section, we identified that the reviewed articles utilized one or more of the following 17 quantitative evaluation metrics.

Overall Accuracy (Acc) is a traditional and straightforward metric for assessing the performance of segmentation models. While it provides a general overview of model performance, it has limitations, especially in scenarios with imbalanced data distributions, such as stroke segmentation [6]. Specificity (Spc), which measures the model’s ability to correctly identify negative cases, faces similar issues. In these cases, a model might achieve high accuracy by favoring the more prevalent class, potentially overlooking critical details in the less common class [75]. A pixel-wise comparison [2] between the model’s segmentation results and the ground truth results in one of the pixel classes listed in Table 7.

Table 7: Categories of segmented pixels compared with ground truth pixels.

Segmented Pixel Class	Segmented Pixels Vs Ground Truth Pixels
True Positive (TP)	The count of lesion pixels in ground truth accurately classified as lesion pixels by the model.
True Negative (TN)	The count of non-lesion pixels in ground truth accurately classified as non-lesion pixels by the model.
False Negative (FN)	The count of lesion pixels in ground truth incorrectly classified as non-lesion pixels by the model.
False Positive (FP)	The count of non-lesion pixels in ground truth incorrectly classified as lesion pixels by the model.

To address the limitations of overall accuracy, the Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) is used to measure the similarity between the predicted lesion segmentation and the ground truth. The DSC is particularly robust in handling class imbalance, making it highly valued in medical imaging. It offers a more balanced evaluation of model performance, especially when dealing with small or irregularly shaped regions, such as stroke lesions [6]. DSC is the most commonly used metric for stroke segmentation; however, several concerns surround its use in medical data. It does not account for TN, making it less effective in datasets with imbalanced classes or small lesions [76]. Additionally, DSC treats FP and FN equally, failing to prioritize errors based on clinical significance. It cannot detect segmentation biases related to lesion shape or location, resulting in similar scores for methods with differing spatial accuracies. Moreover, small FP or FN have a disproportionate impact on DSC for small lesions, while large lesions can inflate the metric, obscuring poor performance on smaller lesions [76].

Similar to DSC, there is an Intersection over Union (IoU), also known as the Jaccard Index. IoU measures the ratio of the intersection between the predicted segmentation and the ground truth to their union. Precision (Prc), or Positive Predictive Value (PPV), further refines the evaluation by assessing the proportion of correctly identified stroke lesion pixels among all pixels classified as lesions by the model, offering insights into the accuracy of lesion identification. In contrast, Sensitivity (Sen), also known as Recall (Rec), measures the model’s ability to correctly identify all actual lesion pixels in the ground truth, reflecting its effectiveness in capturing all TPs [2].

To balance Precision and Sensitivity, the F1-score is often used. Equivalent to DSC, the F1-score is the harmonic mean of Precision and Recall, providing a single metric that considers both FP and FN [77]. In scenarios where detecting lesions is more critical than avoiding FP, the F2-score is beneficial, as it places more emphasis on Sensitivity [78]. The F2-score is particularly useful for ensuring that all lesions are identified, even at the cost of a higher FP rate. Furthermore, the Lesion-wise F1 score evaluates the segmentation model’s ability to detect lesions on a per-lesion basis, rather than pixel-wise accuracy [74, 79].

For spatial accuracy, the Hausdorff Distance (HD) metric measures the maximum distance between the boundary points of the ground truth (gt) and the predicted lesion segmentation (S) [6]. HD is particularly useful for assessing spatial dissimilarity between segmentation boundaries, providing insights into how accurately the predicted lesion segmentation aligns with the actual contours of the lesion. However, since HD can be sensitive to outliers, the 95th Percentile Hausdorff Distance (HD_{95}) is often used as a more robust alternative. HD_{95} calculates the 95th percentile of the boundary distances, reducing the influence of extreme outliers and offering a more representative measure of boundary accuracy [72]. Both HD and HD_{95} are often reported in millimeters or voxel/pixel-based units.

Similarly, the Average Symmetric Surface Distance (ASSD), sometimes referred to as Symmetric Mean Absolute surface Distance (SMAD), measures the average distance between the surfaces of the ground truth (S_{gt}) and predicted (S_s) lesion segmentations, considering both directions. ASSD is defined by the average surface distance (ASD) [24], which is crucial for evaluating the accuracy of lesion boundaries.

To evaluate lesion detection, the Simple Lesion Count (SLC), sometimes referred to as Absolute Lesion Difference (ALD) or Absolute Lesion Count Difference (LCD), measures whether the model effectively detects all lesions or misses some. SLC is calculated as the absolute difference between the number of predicted lesions (NS) and the number of ground truth lesions (N_{gt}) [68]. Lastly, the Absolute Volume Difference (AVD), or Volume Similarity (VSim), provides a direct assessment of how much the predicted lesion volume (VS) deviates from the actual lesion volume (V_{gt}) [77]. Together, these metrics provide a comprehensive framework for assessing the accuracy and reliability of lesion segmentation models. Table 8 summarizes the main 13 evaluation metrics: the range (from worst to best), and their mathematical formula.

3.7 Loss Functions

Choosing the appropriate loss function is crucial for determining the effectiveness of a model, as it directly influences the optimization process and the model’s ability to learn. In this section, we identified that the reviewed articles utilized one or more of 17 loss functions. The majority of these loss functions are region-based, with only three exceptions that are boundary-oriented. Region-based loss functions are commonly used in medical image segmentation because of their ability to effectively capture the shape and distribution of the target regions [80].

The most common loss function in stroke segmentation is the DSC loss, which measures the overlap between predicted and true binary masks, making it effective for imbalanced data. It helps mitigate the dominance of large background areas and focuses on region-level overlap, rather than pixel-wise accuracy. One drawback of the DSC loss function is that it treats false positives and false negatives with equal weight [81]. A modified version of DSC loss, which squares the sums in the denominator to achieve faster convergence [82], is used by some studies like in [78]. Also, another version of DSC loss, is the soft DSC loss [83, 66, 67], which computes the Dice score using predicted probabilities (continuous values) instead of binary masks, enabling smoother gradient flow and better optimization during training. Similarly, but rarely used, IoU loss, which also measures the overlap between predicted regions and ground truth, shares the strengths and weaknesses of DSC loss. Tversky loss [84] is a modification of the DSC loss that introduces parameters to control the balance between FP and FN, making it particularly effective for imbalanced datasets by weighting the impact of each error type using a tunable parameter [81].

Cross Entropy (CE) [85], along with its two versions, Categorical CE (CCE) and Binary CE (BCE), evaluates pixel-wise classification but is sensitive to class imbalance. Since stroke segmentation is typically a binary classification problem, BCE is generally used whenever a study mentions employing CE. The exception to this is with the SPES [24] dataset, which contains multiple labels for different stroke regions. In stroke segmentation, where lesions are small compared to normal brain tissues, CE can cause models to focus on dominant classes and miss small lesions, leading to potential misclassification of minor yet crucial regions. Balanced BCE (BBCE) [10, 63] adjusts the weights of the classes

Table 8: A summary of the quantitative evaluation metrics.

Metric	Range	Mathematical Formula
Acc	0% to 100%	$\frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$
Spc	0 to 1	$\frac{TN + TP}{2 \times TP}$
DSC	0 to 1	$\frac{2 \times TP + FP + FN}{TP}$
IoU	0 to 1	$\frac{TP + FP + FN}{TP}$
Prc/PPV	0 to 1	$\frac{TP + FP}{TP}$
Sen/Rec	0 to 1	$\frac{TP + FN}{TP + FN}$
HD	∞ to 0	$\max \left\{ \sup_{a \in gt} \inf_{b \in S} d(a, b), \sup_{b \in S} \inf_{a \in gt} d(a, b) \right\}$
HD ₉₅	∞ to 0	$95\% \left\{ \sup_{a \in gt} \inf_{b \in S} d(a, b), \sup_{b \in S} \inf_{a \in gt} d(a, b) \right\}$
ASD	-	$\frac{\sum_{a \in S_{gt}} \min_{b \in S_S} d(a, b)}{ S_{gt} }$
ASSD/SMAD	∞ to 0	$\frac{ASD(S_{gt}, S_S) + ASD(S_S, S_{gt})}{2}$
F1-Score	0 to 1	$\frac{2 \times \text{Prc} \times \text{Sen}}{\text{Prc} + \text{Sen}}$
F2-Score	0 to 1	$\frac{5 \times \text{Prc} \times \text{Sen}}{4 \times \text{Prc} + \text{Sen}}$
SLC/ALD/LCD	∞ to 0	$ N_S - N_{gt} $
AVD/VSim	∞ to 0	$\frac{ V_S - V_{gt} }{V_{gt}}$

inversely to their frequency, ensuring the minority class (stroke lesions) has proportional importance while preventing the model from overemphasizing the majority class (background). Focal loss [86] is a dynamically weighted extension of CE, that addresses class imbalance by assigning more weight to hard-to-classify examples such as small lesions. However, it requires careful tuning of hyperparameters, which can add complexity. Sinha et al. [75] combined the DSC loss, Focal loss, and Tversky loss in their Weighted Focal Tversky-Dice loss (wFTD). In medical image segmentation, it is common to combine the strengths of multiple loss functions for better performance. A popular combination is DSC loss and BCE loss, where DSC helps optimize region overlap and BCE focuses on pixel-wise classification, effectively addressing class imbalance and improving segmentation accuracy.

Li et al. [81] proposed Task-Aware Loss (TAL) focuses on both positive and negative samples, using an adjustable focus factor to improve recall and balance precision. It assigns higher weights to focused regions, increasing penalties for false negatives and false positives, while including DSC loss to handle extreme sample imbalance. Chen et al. [87] proposed a combination of Multi-Scale Consistency loss (MSC) and Shape-aware Loss (SA) for semi-supervised 3D segmentation. The MSC loss encourages similar segmentation results from both the student and teacher models by comparing multi-scale features extracted from a discriminator that overlays segmentation regions with input images. The SA loss incorporates 3D signed distance maps, leveraging a mean square error loss to better represent the shape of the lesions. Also, Gómez et al. [73] proposed a class-weighted loss, which assigns higher weights to lesion pixels, ensuring the model pays more attention to underrepresented lesion regions. Furthermore, Ou et al. [29] use an adversarial loss of CGAN network [88]. For a detailed understanding of each study-specific loss function, readers are encouraged to refer to the original articles.

Region-based loss functions [89], like all the above loss functions, often perform poorly when segmenting small lesions because these lesions contribute very little to the overall loss and are therefore overlooked. In contrast, boundary-based loss functions focus on refining region edges, making them more effective for small lesion segmentation, as they are not affected by lesion size [80]. Wu et al. [78] used a boundary-based loss (BL) function with a combination of a

region-based loss and DSC loss and achieved outstanding results. SA loss by Chen et al. [87] and Sobel loss by Du et al. [90] are considered boundary-based loss functions as well.

Table 9 provides an overview of commonly used loss functions along with their mathematical formulas. The loss functions included in the table are those that are well-established and widely recognized. For a detailed understanding of each study-specific loss function, readers are encouraged to refer to the original articles.

Table 9: Loss functions.

Loss	Mathematical Formula
DSC	$\mathcal{L}_{DSC}(y, p) = 1 - \frac{2 \sum_{i=1}^N y_i p_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N y_i + \sum_{i=1}^N p_i}$
IoU	$\mathcal{L}_{IoU}(y, p) = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N y_i p_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N [y_i + p_i - y_i p_i]}$
CE	$\mathcal{L}_{CE}(y, p) = - \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{k \in \Omega} [y_{ik} \log(p_{ik})]$
BCE	$\mathcal{L}_{BCE}(y, p) = - \sum_{i=1}^N [y_i \log(p_i) + (1 - y_i) \log(1 - p_i)]$
Focal	$\mathcal{L}_{Focal}(y, p) = - \sum_{i=1}^N \alpha (1 - p_i)^\gamma y_i \log(p_i) + (1 - \alpha) (p_i)^\gamma (1 - y_i) \log(1 - p_i)$
Tversky	$\mathcal{L}_{Tversky}(y, p) = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N y_i p_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N [y_i p_i + (1 - \alpha)(1 - y_i) p_i + \alpha y_i (1 - p_i)]}$
BL	$\mathcal{L}_{bd}(y, p) = \int_{\Omega} \varphi_y(p) S_{\theta}(p) dp$

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, we present a comprehensive analysis of the findings to highlight the key methodologies and architectures identified in the reviewed papers, as well as the benchmarking results based on their reported evaluation metrics. Here we aim to provide a structured and thorough review of the current landscape, helping to clarify the progress made in this area. Figure 8 presents a chronological timeline of the key reviewed articles, selected based on their novelty and originality. Moreover, the recently introduced Must AI Criteria-10 (MAIC-10) [91] is a concise, ten-item checklist developed to assess the methodological quality of AI studies in medical imaging.

Figure 8: Chronological overview of the key reviewed articles.

4.1 Methods and Architectures

Here we provide a detailed discussion of the methods and architectures employed in the reviewed studies. The models proposed in the reviewed articles are categorized into several distinct groups based on their model dimensionality (operating on either 2D or 3D images), supervision framework, and main method category. These groups include fully-supervised, semi-supervised, and unsupervised frameworks. The fully-supervised models are further divided

Figure 9: A taxonomy of the reviewed studies for MRI acute/sub-acute ischemic stroke lesion segmentation.

into CNN-based methods and Transformer-based methods, with the CNN category including U-Net-based models and attention-based models. The studies will be examined in detail, providing insights into the unique contributions and innovations introduced within each group. Each group is examined in detail, providing insights into the unique contributions, innovations, and performance characteristics introduced by the models.

We also provide a taxonomy of the reviewed models in Figure 9, categorized by the DL technique, architecture, and whether the model operates on 2D or 3D data. Our taxonomy helps to clarify the landscape of DL models in ischemic stroke lesion segmentation, enabling a clearer understanding of how different methods approach this task. Models that do not introduce novel or significant approaches will not be discussed. Additionally, models whose primary contributions focus on MRI image handling or processing will be addressed later in this review article.

Additionally, Table 10 presents comprehensive details for each reviewed article, including critical aspects such as the year of publication, code availability, input data type (2D or 3D), MRI modality or modalities used, training and testing datasets, loss function applied, model architecture, preprocessing techniques employed, and data augmentation strategies. This structured table allows for a comparative analysis of the models and highlights key factors influencing their effectiveness in stroke lesion segmentation.

4.1.1 Fully-Supervised

The fully-supervised models are categorized mainly into CNN-based methods and Transformer-based methods, with the CNN group including U-Net-based and attention-based models.

CNN While some studies have employed straightforward CNN methods, such as Ruthra and Bevi [77], Shah et al. [92], and Pinto et al. [67], others have introduced more innovative and promising approaches.

U-Net-based Models Several studies have utilized U-Net-based architectures, either in their standard form or with various enhancements to improve ischemic stroke lesion segmentation. VGG-UNet [93] combines the traditional U-Net framework with a VGG11 network for improved feature extraction. Halder and Sharmin [94] combined InceptionV3 [95] for global feature extraction with 3D U-Net, which leverages kernel-size variations in InceptionV3 and hierarchical segmentation in 3D U-Net to mitigate overfitting and vanishing gradient issues. Werdiger et al. [16] employed a simple U-Net alongside DenseNet, while Aboudi et al. [96] also leveraged a standard U-Net architecture. In contrast, Brzus et al. [59] utilized a 3D U-Net for volumetric segmentation. Additionally, nnU-Net [97] models have been employed by Jeong et al. [74], Atzori and Tshimanga [98] and Kamel et al. [99], with the latter using a self-configuring nnU-Net that automatically optimizes its hyperparameters for enhanced performance. Furthermore, Llambras et al. [21] combined U-Net for segmentation with a fully connected network for classification with three configurations.

Several studies have proposed innovative modifications to the U-Net architecture to enhance stroke lesion segmentation. Boussselham et al. [7] incorporated the Pennes bioheat equation into U-Net, enabling the generation of thermal images that reflect temperature variations within the stroke region to improve lesion detection. However, the limited resolution of thermal imaging presents challenges in accurately capturing these changes. Abdmouleh et al. [100] introduced

a modified U-Net with multi-path inception blocks, which utilize parallel paths of varying depths for richer feature extraction, efficiently integrating diverse feature maps through an element-wise sum. CSNet [101] introduced a fractal U-Net architecture combined with an initial classifier network. The classifier first identifies the lesion-containing slices, which are then segmented in detail by the fractal U-Net. This fractal design reduces computational demands and false positives while improving segmentation accuracy through a voting mechanism.

ResNet-based models have also been employed for stroke lesion segmentation, particularly to enhance feature extraction and model robustness through residual learning. Brain SegNet [102] employs curriculum learning and it is a 3D refinement network based on a residual architecture for hierarchical feature extraction and a refinement module for multi-level feature aggregation. Also, both 3D ASM [103] and NVAUTO [104] models utilize a SegResNet-based architecture, using the MONAI Auto3Dseg framework [105]. Furthermore, several models have merged the strengths of both U-Net and ResNet architectures to leverage the advantages of both frameworks [44, 60, 106, 107].

Both CNN-Res [60] and Res-CNN [44] combine U-Net and ResNet architectures by utilizing translation blocks for downsampling and residual blocks to prevent the vanishing gradient problem, optimizing both local and broader context understanding. Similarly, CNL-ResUNet [106] integrates U-Net with residual blocks and includes a module that enhances precision by adding classification and localization outputs. The residual blocks improve learning dynamics, while skip connections ensure feature richness across network layers. Finally, Jazzar and Douik [107] proposed a U-Net-based model incorporating a multi-path network to more effectively capture and process diverse feature levels, with dilated convolution blocks at the bottleneck to summarize global information and enhance contextual understanding. Lastly, Bayram et al. [108] evaluated the segmentation performance of five U-Net variants: U-Net, Attention U-Net, Residual U-Net, Attention Residual U-Net, and Residual U-Net++. They experimented with various loss functions, including CE, DSC, IoU, Tversky Loss, and Focal Tversky, and concluded that Attention U-Net combined with IoU loss achieved the best performance.

Attention-based Models Several attention-based models have been developed to enhance ischemic stroke lesion segmentation by improving feature extraction and refining segmentation through attention mechanisms. MSR-CNN [109] utilizes an ensemble of deconvolutional sub-networks, each equipped with Multi-Residual Attention (MRA) blocks, enabling enhanced feature extraction at multiple scales. The model also employs Region of Interest (RoI) alignment, standardizing and focusing the training on relevant image patches, which helps address the class imbalance. The use of masked dropout layers further regulates feature flow within the network, improving segmentation accuracy and efficiency, especially when processing smaller regions. EnigmaNet [75] incorporates multi-scale features Genesis-k blocks in both the encoder and decoder stages, augmented by dual-headed attention gates to refine feature extraction and segmentation. AFMS-Net [110] features an adaptable encoder-decoder architecture with two variants, Single and Dual Adaptive Encoder Block, integrated with an attention mechanism Segmentation Path (SegPath) module. Gómez et al. [73] utilized a hierarchical encoder-decoder architecture enhanced with additive cross-attention modules at each decoder level to emphasize lesion patterns. MCA-DN [111] integrates skip connections with multi-path convolutional attention blocks to prioritize voxel activations and enhance spatial focus on lesions.

Additionally, several U-Net-based architectures have integrated attention mechanisms to enhance segmentation performance. LKA [112] modifies the traditional U-Net architecture by employing large kernels to balance local and global feature extraction. It integrates depth-wise, dilated, and pointwise convolutions, and the use of large-kernel attention mechanisms enhances contextual understanding, allowing the model to outperform traditional downscaling approaches in U-Net. ToC-Net [58] is built on the U-Net++ [113] architecture and integrates channel attention and atrous spatial pyramid pooling (ASPP) modules to improve feature extraction. The inclusion of a Target Calibration module specifically enhances boundary segmentation, addressing challenges such as vague lesion contours and intra-class variability. MSA-Net [114] is based on the U-Net3+ [115] architecture and incorporates the Efficient Pyramid Split Attention (EPSA) module in the encoding phase. The model employs Spatial Pyramid-Coordinate Attention (SPCA) at the bottleneck layer to expand the receptive field. Dual attention mechanisms are used during the decoding process, all working together to enhance feature extraction capabilities. DRANet [116] enhances a U-Net-based architecture by incorporating residual blocks and an attention mechanism to refine feature extraction. The attention module focuses on extracting high-quality features. TSRL-Net [81] integrates a U-Net-based architecture with coarse-grained residual learning and both positive and reverse attention mechanisms. These mechanisms optimize feature extraction and minimize false negatives, which highlight unpredicted residual features and suppress background noise. Similarly, PAMSNNet [117] employed a U-Net3+ [115] architecture, augmented with Efficient Pyramid Split Attention (EPSA) and Spatial Pyramid-Coordinate Attention (SPCA) modules to enhance multi-scale spatial information extraction and expand the receptive field, thus improving feature extraction. Also, 3D-DAGMNET [63] builds upon U-Net3+ [115], it incorporates a Dual Attention Gate (DAG) consisting of a channel attention gate and a spatial attention gate to focus on the most relevant features in both spatial and channel dimensions. Finally, PCMA-UNet [35] also builds on the U-Net3+ [115] architecture, incorporating a hybrid attention mechanism that includes pyramid squeeze attention, coordinate

attention, and multi-scale attention modules. This combination improves spatial detail representation, emphasizing channel-wise dependencies and dynamically adapting to lesions of various sizes and shapes.

Transformer-based Models Attention-based models, often built on CNN architectures, integrate attention mechanisms to emphasize important features and suppress irrelevant ones, enhancing local feature representation. In contrast, vision transformer-based models, replace CNNs entirely and use self-attention mechanisms to process images as sequences of patches, capturing both local and global dependencies. While attention-based models excel at refining local feature extraction, transformers extend the concept of attention to model complex, long-range relationships, making them particularly effective for tasks requiring global context understanding. Transformer-based architectures have introduced innovative methods for stroke lesion segmentation by effectively capturing global contextual information and refining boundary precision.

W-Net [78] employs a hybrid approach where a CNN-based auxiliary generator provides an initial segmentation, followed by a boundary deformation module to refine the segmentation boundaries. A transformer-based segmenter equipped with a boundary constraint module then fine-tunes the boundary precision, enhancing the overall accuracy of the segmentation. SrSNet [68] implements a two-stage segmentation framework. The first stage uses a transformer-based TMSFormer for coarse segmentation, followed by a 2D ResUNet for fine-tuning. Symmetrical Attention Blocks (SAB) are introduced to capture and enhance feature-level bilateral asymmetries within the brain, improving segmentation accuracy. Additionally, a Gradient Entropy strategy is employed for efficient patch selection, optimizing the model’s training process. EDAE-Former [118] utilizes dual attention blocks in both the encoder and decoder stages, which improves segmentation by effectively integrating both local and global features. The Factorizer [72] combines a U-Net-based architecture with transformer blocks that employ low-rank matrix factorization. The model integrates Wrapped NMF modules and uses Shifted Window Matricize techniques to optimize the balance between capturing global context and maintaining local relevance which improves segmentation performance. TransRender [119] leverages a multi-scale transformer-based encoder to capture long-range dependencies and a render-based decoder to adaptively select and refine critical points along lesion boundaries. Finally, AGMR-Net [90] combines 2D and 3D convolutions for feature extraction with a coarse-grained patch attention module to focus on critical regions. The model further incorporates cross-dimensional feature fusion to improve boundary delineation, along with multiscale deconvolution upsampling to restore spatial and boundary details lost during downsampling.

Other Fully-Supervised Models Additionally, one study employed a Vision-Language Model (VLM), called SAT [120], which integrates a Transformer-based architecture with a U-Net backbone, utilizing text prompts to guide the segmentation process. Designed to handle multiple imaging modalities and anatomical regions, the model leverages a large, diverse dataset. By integrating textual and visual features through a multimodal knowledge-enhanced framework, the SAT model achieves universal segmentation across various medical imaging tasks, significantly improving its adaptability and performance. Another supervised model is RFDCR [121], which is a Random Forest (RF) classifier with dense Conditional Random Fields (CRF). RF classifiers are trained using intensity-based features and template-based asymmetric features to generate preliminary segmentation maps, which are then integrated with optimized probability maps derived from dense CRF. This layered approach leverages both local appearance and global contextual information, iteratively enhancing segmentation precision. Furthermore, FANTOM [122] employs federated learning and uses a VGG-inspired architecture trained with adversarial learning, featuring two relativistic discriminators to distinguish core and penumbra regions.

4.1.2 Semi-Supervised

Three semi-supervised models have been proposed for ischemic stroke lesion segmentation for the context of limited annotated data. MTANS [87] introduced a model that merges a mean teacher-student strategy with adversarial networks. This model leverages both labeled and unlabeled data, where the student model, under the guidance of the teacher model, generates probability maps and signed distance maps (SDM). These outputs are further examined by a discriminator that enforces shape-aware consistency and multi-scale regularization through adversarial learning. Also, two studies have employed few-shot learning models. Alshehri and Muhammad [123] proposed a few-shot model based on the VGG-16 architecture, integrating self-attention mechanisms and prototypical networks to effectively handle few-shot learning scenarios. By leveraging prototypical networks, the system learns from a small number of annotated examples, reducing computational load by excluding unlesioned slices and focusing attention on significant regions through self-attention, thereby enhancing segmentation performance. Similarly, the SIGN model [124] utilizes a self-ensembling approach with the Identify-to-Discern Network (IDN), combined with a Soft Distribution-aware Updating (SDU) strategy. This model improves stroke lesion segmentation in low-quality and few-shot MRI data by employing transfer learning from glioma data in the BraTS 2020 dataset. IDN initially identifies potential lesion areas in low-quality MRIs, while SDU refines these predictions by adapting the learning process based on the similarities between glioma and stroke lesion characteristics.

Table 10: Comprehensive overview of the reviewed articles.

Model	Year	Code	Dataset	Modality(s)	Input	Architecture	Loss	Preprocessing	Augmentation	Evaluation Metrics
TSRL-Net [81]	2023	Yes	SISS	T1	2D	ResUNet + Attention	TAL	Crop, Norm.	VF, HF	DSC: 0.79, IoU: 0.53, Prec: 0.63, Sen: 0.69
Posterior-CRF [79]	2022	Yes	SISS	DWI-FLAIR-T1-T2	3D	R-CNN	DSC	Crop, Gaussian Norm, PE.	Rotate, Shift, HF.	DSC: 0.61, Sen: 0.65, HD95: 25.2, AVD: 0.48, Lesion-wise F1: 0.56
SIGN [124]	2022	Yes	SISS	FLAIR-T1-T2	3D	few-shot + self-ensemble	IoU	Resize, GS, Norm.	-	DSC: 0.77, Acc: 0.77, HD: 0.98
MTANS [87]	2021	Yes	SISS	-	3D	Knowledge Distillation	MSC + SA + BCE	BFC, Z-score Norm, PE.	-	(20% of labels) DSC: 0.69, Prec: 0.68, Sen: 0.80, HD: 29.8, ASSD: 3.51
EnigmaNet [75]	2024	No	SISS	DWI-FLAIR	2D	Attention	wFTD	Norm, Resize.	Rotate, Flip, Shear, Zoom.	DSC: 0.90, Sen: 0.88, Spc: 0.99
CNL-ResUNet [106]	2024	No	SISS	DWI-FLAIR-T1-T2	2D	ResUNet	DSC + BCE	Resize to 192x192, SS, Norm.	HF, Zoom, Shear, Rotate.	DSC: 0.83, Acc: 0.97
AOK-Means [71]	2023	No	SISS	DWI	2D	K-Means clustering	-	CLAHE.	-	DSC: 0.76, Prec: 0.92, Sen: 0.70, Acc: 0.99
Alshehri & Muh. [123]	2023	No	SISS	DWI-FLAIR	2D	few-shot + VGG16 + Attention Fuzzy C-Means clustering	CE	SS, Norm.	Rotate, Scale, Flip, Shear, Zoom.	DSC: 0.68, IoU: 0.75, Sen: 0.61
HBFEFCM [70]	2023	No	SISS	DWI-FLAIR-T1-T2	2D	Fuzzy C-Means clustering	-	Norm, HisC.	-	DSC: 0.80, Prec: 0.96, Sen: 0.85, Acc: 0.99
MidFusNet [16]	2023	No	SISS	DWI-FLAIR-T1-T2	3D	DenseNet	CE	SS, Norm, PE.	Rotate, Flip, Scale.	DSC: 0.63
AGMR-Net [90]	2022	No	SISS	T1	3D	Transformer	Focal + DSC + CE + Sobel	SS, Norm, Crop, Resize.	-	DSC: 0.75, Prec: 0.63, Sen: 0.62
Jazzar & Douik [107]	2022	No	SISS	DWI-FLAIR-T1-T2	2D	U-Net + ResNet	DSC	Norm.	-	DSC: 0.84
Aboudi et al. [96]	2022	No	SISS	DWI-FLAIR-T1-T2	2D	U-Net	CE	Norm, Resize to 128x128, Crop, Norm.	Rotate, Flip, Zoom, Shear.	DSC: 0.56, Prec: 0.99, Acc: 0.999
Abdmouleh et al. [100]	2022	No	SISS	DWI-FLAIR-T1-T2	2D	U-Net	CE	Resize to 192x192.	Rotate, Flip.	DSC: 0.81, Sen: 0.80, Acc: 0.97, Spc: 0.99
MSR-CNN [109]	2021	No	SISS	DWI-FLAIR-T1-T2	2D	ResNet + Attention	DSC + CCE	Resize, min-max Norm.	RC, Flip, Rotate.	DSC: 0.78, IoU: 0.86, Prec: 0.75, Sen: 0.80, Spc: 0.95
VGG-UNet [93]	2021	No	SISS	FLAIR	2D	U-Net + VGG11	CE	Resize to 256x256.	HF, VF, Rotate.	DSC: 0.95, IoU: 0.91, Acc: 0.987
RFDRC [121]	2020	No	SISS	FLAIR-T1-T1c-T2	3D	RF	-	SS, Norm, BFC.	-	DSC: 0.48, Prec: 0.43, Sen: 0.75, HD: 45.9, ASSD: 11.7
MPFN [125]	2020	No	SISS	DWI	2D	CNN	DSC + CE	BFC, Norm.	HF, VF, RC.	DSC: 0.62, IoU: 0.45, Sen: 0.73, Acc: 0.999
DRANet [116]	2020	No	SISS	DWI-FLAIR-T1-T2 (all combinations)	2D	ResUNet + Attention	DSC	SS, Norm.	-	DSC: 0.76, HD: 3.19
Shah et al. [92]	2020	No	SISS	-	2D	Traditional CNN	-	SS, PE, Register.	-	DSC: 0.71
Raina et al. [49]	2020	No	SISS	FLAIR	2D	CNN	DSC	SS, Norm.	-	DSC: 0.62, Prec: 0.68, Sen: 0.60
Bal et al. [126]	2023	No	SISS, SPES	All modalities separately	3D	CNN	DSC	Norm, NR, BFC, PE.	Rotate, Flip.	(SISS/SPES) DSC: 0.87/0.90, Prec: 0.88/0.9, Sen: 0.86/0.89
MIRW [69]	2021	No	SISS, SPES	All modalities separately and some combinations	3D	Random Walker	-	Norm, OR, HisT.	-	(SISS/SPES) DSC: 0.89/0.88, Prec: 0.87/0.78, Sen: 0.93/0.65, Spc: 0.99/0.96
CSNet [101]	2020	No	SISS, SPES, ISLES17	-	3D	U-Net	DSC + BCE	Norm, Resize to 256x256.	Rotate, Flip.	(SISS/SPES/ISLES17) DSC: 0.88/0.90/0.67, Prec: 0.88/0.91/0.61, Sen: 0.90/0.99/0.66, Acc: 0.99/0.99/0.99
MCA-DN [111]	2021	No	SISS, SPES, ISLES17	DWI-PWI	2D	ResNet + Attention	BCE	Norm, Resize.	-	(SISS/SPES/ISLES17) DSC: 0.79/0.85/0.47, Sen: 0.91/0.92/0.87, Spc: 0.99/0.99/0.97
FANTOM [122]	2024	No	SPES	DWI-Tmax-TTP	2D	VGG	BCE + Adversarial	Resize to 128x128, min-max Norm.	-	DSC: 0.77, Prec: 0.77, Sen: 0.78

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Model	Year	Code	Dataset	Modality(s)	Input	Architecture	Loss	Preprocessing	Augmentation	Evaluation Metrics
CNN-Res [60]	2023	No	SPES	DWI-FLAIR	2D	U-Net + ResNet	DSC	-	Rotate, Flip.	DSC: 0.79
Bousselham et al. [7]	2022	No	SPES	-	2D	U-Net	DSC	Norm, Crop, Resize to 96x96.	HF, VF Rotate.	DSC: 0.93, Prec: 0.92, Sen: 0.95, Acc: 0.99
Res-CNN [44]	2020	No	SPES	DWI-T2	2D	U-Net + ResNet	DSC	Norm, SS, Register to DWI, GS.	Rotate, Flip.	DSC: 0.88, HD: 1.63
Gómez et al. [73]	2023	No	ISLES17	ADC, TTP, Tmax combinations	2D	Attention	Focal + Class-Weighted Loss	Resize to 224x224, min-max Norm	Rotate, BA, CA, Flip, ED, Grid and Optical Distortions	DSC: 0.36, Prec: 0.42, Sen: 0.48
Bayram et al. [108]	2022	No	ISLES17	-	2D	U-Net + Attention	IoU	Resize to 128x128, min-max Norm	-	DSC: 0.77, IoU: 0.62, Prec: 0.81, HD: 0.73, Acc: 0.99, Spc: 0.99
Halder & Sharmin [94]	2024	No	ISLES17	ADC, rCBF, rCBV, MTT, Tmax, TTP (6-channel input)	3D	U-Net + InceptionV3	DSC + Focal	Resize to 256x256x32, min-max Norm	-	DSC: 0.43, Prec: 0.58, Sen: 0.36
Brain SegNet [102]	2020	No	ISLES17	-	3D	ResNet	Focal	SS, Norm, Crop, Resize	Rotate, Flip, Scale, RC, Intensity Adjustment	DSC: 0.3, Prec: 0.35, Sen: 0.43
Pinto et al. [67]	2021	No	ISLES17	ADC, Tmax, TTP, MTT, rCBF, rCBV combinations	3D	U-Net + ResNet	Soft DSC	Resize to 256x256x32, BFC, Norm, Clip	-	DSC: 0.3, Prec: 0.29, Sen: 0.63, HD: 33.94, ASSD: 5.99
Pinto et al. [66]	2021	Yes	ISLES17	ADC, Tmax, TTP, MTT, rCBF, rCBV combinations	3D	U-Net + LSTM	Soft DSC	Resize to 256x256x32, Norm, Clip	Rotate	DSC: 0.38, Prec: 0.41, Sen: 0.53, HD: 29.21, ASSD: 5.52
Jeong et al. [74]	2024	Yes	ISLES22	DWI-ADC, DWI	3D	nnU-Net	DSC + BCE	Crop, Non-zero Norm, Zero Norm	Rotate, ED, HF, Scale, GB, GN, BA, CA, GT	DSC: 0.78, LCD: 2.1, AVD: 5.1, Lesion-wise F1-score: 0.82
Werdiger et al. [16]	2024	Yes	ISLES22	DWI-ADC	3D	U-Net + DenseNet	DSC	SS	-	DSC: 0.69
Factorizer [72]	2023	Yes	ISLES22	DWI-ADC	3D	Transformer + U-Net	DSC + CE	Crop, Zero Norm, PE	RAT (Flip, Smooth, Scale, Shift), GN, GT	DSC: 0.76, HD95: 12
SAT [120]	2023	Yes	ISLES22	-	3D	VLM + U-Net	DSC + BCE	Reorient, RSM, Norm	RC, Zoom, Scale	DSC: 0.65
LKA [112]	2023	Yes	ISLES22	DWI-ADC-FLAIR	3D	U-Net + Attention	DSC + CE	SS, Crop, Norm	Rotate, RC, Scale	DSC: 0.69, F1: 0.66, LCD: 3.7, AVD: 6.1
PCMA-UNet [35]	2024	No	ISLES22	DWI	2D	U-Net3+ + Attention	BCE	-	-	DSC: 0.78, IoU: 0.69, Prec: 0.86, Sen: 0.80
AFMS-Net [110]	2024	No	ISLES22	DWI-ADC-FLAIR	3D	Attention	DSC + Focal	Register to MNI, Crop, Resize to 128x128x128, Norm, GS.	-	DSC: 0.82, IoU: 0.68, Prec: 0.84, Sen: 0.78, Acc: 0.995, AHD: 9.9
SrSNet [68]	2024	No	ISLES22	DWI-ADC	2D	Transformer + ResUNet	DSC	RSM, Norm, GH.	RC, HF	DSC: 0.79, IoU: 0.68, Sen: 0.78, HD95: 10.2, F2: 0.79, LCD: 3.2, AVD: 1.7
PAMSNet [117]	2024	No	ISLES22	DWI	2D	U-Net3+ + Attention	BCE	RSM, Norm.	Scale, HF.	DSC: 0.88, IoU: 0.81, Prec: 0.91, Sen: 0.90, HD: 4.4
MSA-Net [114]	2024	No	ISLES22	DWI	2D	UNet3+ + Attention	BCE	Resize to 256x256, Norm.	RAT (Scale, Flip), GT.	DSC: 0.87, IoU: 0.79, Prec: 0.91, Sen: 0.88, HD: 3.2
Kamel et al. [99]	2024	No	ISLES22	Combinations of DWI-ADC-FLAIR	3D	nnU-Net	-	Register, SS, RSM, Norm.	-	DSC: 0.81
EDAE-Former [118]	2024	No	ISLES22	-	2D	Transformer	DSC + CE	Resize to 224x224, Norm.	-	DSC: 0.70, HD95: 13.4
Llambias et al. [21]	2024	No	ISLES22	FLAIR	2D	U-Net	DSC + CE	Resize, Norm.	Rotate, ED, Add Noise.	DSC: 0.32, AVD: 0.54
BBox-Guided Seg. [29]	2023	No	ISLES22	DWI-eADC	3D	GAN + Transformer	CE + Adversarial	Resize to 256x256.	-	DSC: 0.84, IoU: 0.83
W-Net [78]	2023	No	ISLES22	DWI-ADC-FLAIR	2D	Transformer	DSC + Boundary-Based Loss	Resize to 208x176, Register to ADC and DWI.	-	DSC: 0.86, Prec: 0.88, Sen: 0.85, HD: 27.3, F2: 0.85
TransRender [119]	2023	No	ISLES22	DWI-ADC-FLAIR	2D	Transformer	DSC + BCE	Resize to 208x176.	-	DSC: 0.85, Prec: 0.86, Sen: 0.84, HD: 27.6, F2: 0.85

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Model	Year	Code	Dataset	Modality(s)	Input	Architecture	Loss	Preprocessing	Augmentation	Evaluation Metrics
3D ASM [103]	2023	No	ISLES22	DWI-ADC	3D	SegResNet	-	RSM, Norm, Resize to 192x192x128.	Flip, Rotate, Scale, Smooth, GN, RC.	DSC: 0.85, Acc: 0.99, F1-score: 0.87, LCD: 1.0, AVD: 1.6
Brzus et al. [59]	2023	No	ISLES22	-	3D	U-Net	DSC + CE	Crop, Norm, RSM, GS.	Rotate, Zoom, Flip.	DSC: 0.64
Ruthra & Bevi [77]	2023	No	ISLES22	DWI	3D	CNN	-	Norm.	-	DSC: 0.82, Acc: 0.99, F1: 0.8, LCD: 2.3, AVD: 1.15
ToC-Net [58]	2023	No	ISLES22	-	2D	UNet++ + Attention	-	-	-	DSC: 0.87, IoU: 0.77, Pre: 0.93, Sen: 0.84, HD: 3.72
NVAUTO [104]	2022	No	ISLES22	DWI-ADC	3D	SegResNet	DSC + Focal	RSM, Norm.	Flip, Rotate, Scale, Smooth, GN, Shift, RC.	DSC: 0.82, LCD: 2.0, AVD: 1.634, HD: 27.34, F1: 0.8
Atzori & Tshim. [98]	2022	No	ISLES22	DWI-ADC	3D	nnUNet	DSC + CE	Crop, Norm.	-	DSC: 0.66
3D-DAGMNet [63]	2021	No	JHUS	DWI-ADC-b0	3D	UNet3+ + Attention	DSC + BBCE	Gaussian Norm, Resize to 96x112x48.	-	DSC: 0.76, Pre: 0.83, Sen: 0.73
Liu et al. [25]	2023	No	JHUS	DWI	2D	U-Net	-	-	-	DSC: 0.74
End of the table.										

4.1.3 Weakly Supervised

In weakly supervision, only one model has been proposed. BBox-Guided Segmentor [29] is a patcher encoder combined with bounding box annotations that refines segmentation predictions via adversarial learning. A discriminator generates pixel-wise confidence maps, and pseudo-labels are derived from weak annotations to improve segmentation accuracy.

4.1.4 Unsupervised Models

In the area of unsupervised learning, three models have been introduced. MIRW [69] uses a global volumetric histogram for automated seed-point detection and applies a random walker algorithm to segment lesions, but unfortunately, it is computationally intensive. HBFECM [70] enhances traditional Fuzzy C-Means clustering, which begins with morphological reconstruction to prepare the image, followed by histogram-based clustering to better identify potential lesion areas. The algorithm further applies a median filter to the membership functions, allowing the integration of spatial information for improved segmentation outcomes. AOK-Means [71] builds on traditional K-Means clustering by addressing its limitations, which are the random selection of initial cluster centers and determining the optimal number of clusters. Furthermore, Pinto et al. [66] combine unsupervised learning with supervised learning by integrating a two-pathway Restricted Boltzmann Machine (RBM) to generate structural features for blood flow and lesion maps, combined with U-Net enhanced with Long-Short Term Memory (LSTM). It uses RBM for unsupervised feature extraction, and the supervised stage combines U-Net with LSTM to incorporate spatial and temporal contextual information.

4.2 Benchmarking

In this section, we explore the benchmarking of the reviewed models by evaluating and comparing their performance using the DSC metric, as this is the only metric that is used by all the reviewed articles. Here we highlight the top two or three models, particularly when their performance metrics are closely aligned. The availability of a model’s code online enhances its trustworthiness, as it allows for greater transparency and reproducibility. However, the absence of publicly available code does not necessarily imply that the study is of low quality or should be disregarded. It is noteworthy that four papers [69, 101, 111, 126] analyzed multiple public datasets and conducted independent training and testing on each dataset. Furthermore, the performance of methods in the field has shown only marginal improvements over the years (see Figure 10), with comparable performance observed between earlier and more recent studies across all datasets. In Fig 10, the horizontal line in a specific year indicates that only a single study was conducted for this dataset during that year.

4.2.1 ISLES 2015-SISS

For ISLES 2015-SISS dataset [24], 25 articles were reviewed, among these, 4 studies provided their code online [79, 81, 87, 124]. Additionally, 5 studies [69, 70, 87, 123, 124] employed non-fully supervised frameworks, making them incompatible with benchmarking alongside the other fully supervised methods. Consequently, 21 fully supervised models [16, 49, 70, 71, 75, 79, 81, 90, 92, 93, 96, 100, 101, 106, 107, 109, 111, 116, 121, 125, 126] were included in the benchmark.

Among the fully supervised models, VGG-UNet [93], EnigmaNet [75], and CSNet [101] achieved the highest DSC, scoring 0.95, 0.90, and 0.88, respectively. Two studies, HBFECM [70] and MIRW [69] utilized unsupervised

Figure 10: DSC scores over the years for each dataset.

frameworks, with MIRW demonstrating superior performance. Furthermore, three studies employed semi-supervised frameworks: MTANS [87], Alshehri and Muhammad [123], and SIGN [124], with SIGN delivering the best results among them.

4.2.2 ISLES 2015-SPES

For ISLES 2015-SPES dataset [24], 8 articles were reviewed, among these, 4 of them overlapped with those reviewed for the SISS dataset. Consequently, 7 articles employing fully supervised models [7, 44, 60, 101, 111, 122, 126], were seemed suitable for benchmarking, alongside one study [69] utilizing an unsupervised framework.

Among the fully supervised models, Bousselham et al. [7], Bal et al. [126] and CSNet [101] achieved the highest DSC scores, reaching 0.93, 0.90, and 0.90, respectively.

4.2.3 ISLES 2017

For the ISLES 2017 dataset [26], 8 articles were reviewed. Among these, 2 articles overlapped with those reviewed for the SISS and SPES datasets. Consequently, 6 articles employing fully supervised models were deemed suitable for benchmarking, alongside 2 studies [73, 94, 101, 102, 108, 111] were deemed suitable for benchmarking, alongside 2 studies [66, 67] that utilized semi-supervised frameworks.

Among the fully supervised models, Bayram et al. [108] and CSNet [101] demonstrated superior performance, achieving DSC scores of 0.77 and 0.67, respectively. Regarding the semi-supervised frameworks proposed by Pal et al. [66, 67], both studies share significant similarities in their methodologies. However, one study [66] demonstrated superior performance compared to the other.

4.2.4 ISLES 2022

For ISLES 2022 dataset [22], 22 articles were reviewed, among them, 5 studies provided their code online [16, 72, 74, 112, 120]. Consequently, 21 articles [16, 21, 35, 58, 59, 68, 72, 74, 77, 78, 98, 99, 103, 104, 110, 112, 114, 117, 118, 119, 120] of fully supervised models, were seemed suitable for benchmarking. Additionally, one study [29] employed a weakly supervised method.

PAMSNet [117] achieved the highest DSC of 0.88, followed closely by MSA-Net [114] and ToC-Net [58], both with DSC scores of 0.87.

4.2.5 JHUS

For the JHUS dataset [25], the only models utilized this dataset are those trained in the dataset’s publication [25], and the models trained in an earlier study by the dataset’s authors, published two years before its official release [63].

Among these, 3D-DAGMNet [63] achieved a DSC of 0.76, which is higher than all the other models. It is worth noting that 3D-DAGMNet [63] was designed for this dataset prior to the official release, raising the question of whether the same data was used in this study.

5 RECOMMENDATIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

The selection and preparation of input data can be optimized by carefully reviewing the literature. Here, we aim to analyze three critical aspects: input data dimensionality, the MRI modalities utilized, and the preprocessing and augmentation techniques employed. Our objective is to highlight the most commonly adopted practices, identify innovative approaches, and explore potential future directions in these areas.

5.1 Input Data Dimensionality

The input data type of 53% of the studies was 2D (32 studies), while the other 47% were 3D (28 studies). Each type of data has its own set of advantages and limitations when it comes to lesion segmentation. There is no definitive answer as to whether 2D or 3D models are inherently superior; their segmentation performance is highly situational and depends on various factors specific to the model design. Notably, several 2D models have demonstrated exceptional performance, such as [75, 78, 111, 114, 117], while many 3D models have also achieved outstanding results, including [101, 126]. However, the majority of the top-performing models identified in this review primarily operated on 2D images.

However, one of the main drawbacks of 2D models is the loss of spatial information, which is crucial for accurately identifying stroke lesions that extend across multiple slices. Interestingly, two methods [90, 127] proposed a fusion of 2D and 3D convolutions for feature extraction on the ATLAS dataset. Interestingly, a study by Ou et al. [55] suggests using 2.5D data which combines adjacent 2D slices as multi-channel input to capture limited 3D spatial context while using a 2D model.

On the other hand, 3D data presents its own challenges, particularly the high memory requirements, which can exceed the capacity of GPUs. To address this, down-sampling is often applied, but this can result in a loss of important information. An alternative approach is the use of patching techniques, which reduce memory demands without losing data. Patching also helps mitigate class imbalance, as it ensures a more even representation of both healthy and lesion areas in stroke segmentation tasks [14, 126].

Usually, axial 2D slices are used as input, but an interesting technique discussed by four studies [69, 79, 118, 125] involves using 2D slices from multiple planes—coronal, sagittal, and axial. These three perspectives capture lesions from different angles, allowing the model to develop a more comprehensive understanding of the lesion’s shape, size, and location. This approach is particularly beneficial as 2D models often lose spatial information when relying on slices from a single view. By incorporating multiple views, the model preserves more of the lesion’s spatial context, which should lead to improved accuracy.

5.2 Small Lesions

The accurate segmentation of stroke lesions is essential for effective diagnosis and treatment planning, yet it remains particularly challenging, especially for small lesions. Although small lesions are a well-recognized challenge, few have explored effective strategies to address them.

Shang et al. [128] introduced two labeling strategies to enhance the segmentation of small lesions: Multi-Size Labeling (MSL) and Distance-Based Labeling (DBL). MSL categorizes lesion masks into different classes based on lesion size, enabling the model to focus more effectively on smaller lesions. DBL, on the other hand, emphasizes boundary regions by categorizing lesion voxels into boundary and interior areas, improving segmentation precision near lesion edges. These strategies are combined using an ensemble approach, where small lesion predictions are derived from a weighted interpolation of MSL and DBL outputs, which reported to result an improved segmentation accuracy for small lesions.

An another approach could involve leveraging a model with a hierarchical encoder specifically designed to preserve larger spatial dimensions in feature maps, ensuring small lesions remain detectable even during the down-sampling process. By prioritizing high-resolution features and retaining critical spatial information, such models can effectively overcome the limitations of CNN-based methods, significantly improving their ability to accurately segment small lesions.

5.3 Preprocessing and Augmentation

Preprocessing is a crucial step in medical image segmentation as it directly influences the quality of input data and, consequently, the performance of the model. The most used preprocessing techniques in the reviewed articles are intensity normalization (in its four variations), resizing, and cropping. Additionally, data augmentation has been an important key to enhance model performance and mitigate overfitting. The most frequently used augmentation techniques in the reviewed articles are rotation, flipping, skull stripping, and scaling.

A promising approach in augmentation is the generation of synthetic images using GANs, which potentially can enrich the training datasets. For example, Wu et al. [129] successfully employed GANs to generate synthetic stroke images. A novel method introduced by Ahmed et al. [130] involves extracting lesions from lesioned MRI scans and inserting them into healthy MRI scans. These methods could be valuable in addressing challenges such as data scarcity, class imbalance, and the high cost of obtaining labeled data. By generating synthetic datasets, they provide a cost-effective and scalable solution to enhance training and improve model performance in such scenarios. Furthermore, researchers now can use the toolbox of Chalcraft et al. [131] which uses a novel lesion-pasting method for stroke lesion segmentation.

As shown in Figure 11, the first box plot represents the DSC scores for all reviewed studies on the specific dataset, while the second and third box plots display the DSC scores for 2D and 3D models, respectively. Since only aggregate DSC scores were available for the reviewed models, statistical testing was not applicable. The performance of methods appears comparable between 2D and 3D input data, with 3D leading in some datasets and 2D in others. Additionally, studies vary in whether they use data augmentation or not, the fourth and fifth box plots present the DSC scores of studies that employed augmentation techniques compared to those that did not. Each box includes a horizontal line representing the median DSC, while the central 'x' marker denotes the mean DSC score. The whiskers extend to indicate the range from the minimum to the maximum DSC values within each category, and any outliers are displayed as separate points marked with an 'o.' In the plots, "Aug" refers to studies utilizing augmentation techniques, and "All" encompasses all reviewed studies.

Figure 11: Box-plots illustrating DSC performance across all studies, comparing 2D/3D data types and the use of augmentation techniques.

5.4 MRI Modality

The most used MRI input for SISS is a four-channel configuration comprising DWI, FLAIR, T1, and T2. In contrast, for the other datasets, no specific set of modalities has emerged as a dominant focus across the reviewed articles. The use of multiple MRI modalities in segmentation tasks theoretically enhances performance by combining different MR

contrasts and maps. However, this is not always the case. Some studies use single-modality input, such as DWI or T1, while others employ multi-channel inputs that combine modalities like ADC, FLAIR, T2, or Tmax. Additionally, certain articles explore various modality combinations to determine the most effective pairing.

Kamel et al. [99] reported no significant improvement when adding ADC and FLAIR to DWI. Jeong et al. [74] observed that DWI alone sometimes performs better, while DWI-ADC combinations offer slightly improved results. Gómez et al. [73] found that multi-channel input using ADC-TTP-Tmax outperformed individual modalities.

Several studies suggest FLAIR as a superior modality. Sinha et al. [75] and Vupputuri and Ghosh [69] both reported FLAIR as more effective than DWI, while Abdmouleh et al. [100] concluded FLAIR was the best modality without testing combinations. Conversely, Jazzar et al. [106] identified DWI as the best single modality but did not explore combinations. Liu et al. [116] noted FLAIR-DWI as the most effective combination, outperforming individual modalities.

Some studies compared combinations against single modalities. Thiyagarajan and Murugan [2] found DWI alone superior to combinations with T1, T2, or FLAIR, and slightly better than FLAIR. Alshehri and Muhammad [123] reported that FLAIR-DWI performed better than FLAIR-T1. Liu et al. [44] also observed that DWI-T2 combinations surpassed DWI alone.

Ultimately, no agreement exists on the optimal combination of MRI modalities, as results vary significantly across studies and datasets. However, the best-performing models for each dataset primarily utilize a single MRI modality, with DWI being the most commonly employed.

When using 2D images as input data from multiple MRI modalities, they are typically fed as multi-channel images. However, a promising approach discussed by three studies [28, 69, 98] suggests using a fusing model with three separate encoders, each dedicated to processing a specific MRI modality. This design allows the model to extract modality-specific features in parallel, leading to a more detailed and nuanced understanding of the data. After the features are extracted, they are typically fused before the decoder, enabling the model to integrate information from the different channels for improved performance in segmentation tasks. Moreover, an idea proposed by Liu et al. [44] suggests that using a combination of DWI and DWI-T2, denoted as DWI+(DWI-T2), achieves better results than DWI alone.

5.5 Methods and Architectures

While UNet-based and transformer-based models have demonstrated promising results in stroke segmentation, there remains a significant gap before their performance reaches a level of perfection suitable for clinical adoption. Emerging directions in computer vision, such as Vision-Language Models (VLMs) and Large Language Models (LLMs), offer new opportunities to bridge this gap and enhance model reliability and applicability in clinical settings.

VLMs represent a new direction in deep learning, where both visual and textual data are jointly modeled to enhance tasks such as image classification and segmentation. VLMs can be used for stroke segmentation in various ways, like integrating information from both vision and textual information, VLMs can provide more robust and context-aware predictions, which can be valuable in medical imaging tasks like ischemic stroke segmentation, where both visual features (e.g., MRI scans) and textual annotations (e.g., clinical reports) can be leveraged. Vision-Language Models (VLMs) can enhance stroke segmentation by utilizing models like ChatGPT to generate a detailed textual description of the image, highlighting key features and significant regions. This textual context can then guide the VLM, enabling it to focus on relevant areas and achieve more precise segmentation results. Furthermore, VLMs can be leveraged by developing systems that allow clinicians to refine segmentation via textual prompts. One of the most prominent examples of VLMs is CLIP (Contrastive Language-Image Pretraining) [132], and building on its success, specialized models like MedCLIP [133], and BioViL-T [134], have emerged, focusing specifically on medical imaging. Only one model in this review used VLM, which is SAT [120] that utilizes text prompts to guide the segmentation process.

LLMs such as GPT [135] or BERT [136], can play a transformative role in stroke segmentation by providing advanced multimodal reasoning capabilities. LLMs can be used to integrate patient reports with imaging data for context-aware segmentation. Also, it can be utilized to generate synthetic patient data or textual prompts to augment training datasets and improve model generalization.

CONCLUSION

This review article presents a comprehensive analysis of the current advancements and challenges in the segmentation of acute and sub-acute ischemic stroke lesions using DL techniques in MRI images. By systematically reviewing studies from 2020 onward, 60 articles met the inclusion criteria and were analyzed, providing insights into their

methodologies, input data dimensionality, MRI modalities, preprocessing, augmentation techniques, and evaluation metrics. We identified 31 private datasets from as early as 2015, which highlights the significant impact these private datasets could have had if they had been made publicly available.

Benchmarking analysis revealed that the most widely used datasets are ISLES 2015-SISS and ISLES 2022, while SPES and ISLES 2017 were less frequently utilized. For the JHUS dataset, its limited use can be attributed to its very recent introduction to the field (in 2023). Fully supervised models such as PAMNet, CSNet, and MCADN consistently demonstrated high performance. Moreover, the reliability of studies is brought into question when code is not provided, as transparency and reproducibility are critical to establishing trustworthiness in this field. Another crucial aspect is the question of generalizability, where researchers are encouraged to evaluate their methods on new, unseen datasets to foster confidence and reproducibility.

However, unsupervised, semi-supervised, and weakly supervised frameworks also showed promise, particularly in scenarios with limited labeled data, which can open new avenues for future studies. Finally, this review serves as a foundational reference for researchers aiming to contribute to this critical area of DL-powered MRI-based stroke segmentation. We proposed several future directions and focused on the key challenges of this field. By addressing the challenges in stroke segmentation and leveraging advancements in DL, the field can advance diagnostic precision and therapeutic outcomes for ischemic stroke patients

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